

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Annex 1.7 to AD4.1 – Assent Form for Children

WP 4

Partnership
FOR THE
Assessment
OF
Risks
FROM
Chemicals

Co-funded by
the European Union

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Project approved by *[specify name of the committee]* with ref. n° XXXXX

PARC TASK 4.1 TEMPLATE

ASSENT FORM FOR CHILDREN PARTICIPANTS

[title of study, e.g. PARC aligned study on [specify name of pollutant(s)]

INSTRUCTIONS ON HOW TO USE THIS TEMPLATE

This document is a template, which can be used to develop an assent form for children participants in PARC surveys, if demanded by the study design and national requirements. You may introduce changes, to meet those requirements. To use this template, adjust the text as you find appropriate for your study.

The PARC templates for children are:

"CH_IL – Information leaflet": Information Leaflet for Children Participants (6-11 years).

"CH_QA – Questions and Answers": Questions and Answers for Children Participants (6-11 years).

"CH_AF – Assent form": Assent form for Children Participants (6-11 years).

"CH_FS – Fact Sheet": Fact sheet on chemicals for Children Participants (6-11 years).

"ADOL-CH_CIC - Consent Form Parent or Legal Guardian": "Adjusted Consent Form for Parents / Legal Guardians of Young Participants".

Assent Form for Children (6-11 years)

To be completed by the child, in the presence of their parents/ guardians

Dear child,

Please circle all you agree with:

	YES	NO
Has somebody explained the study to you?		
Do you understand what the study is about?		
Have you asked all the questions you want?		
Have you had your questions answered in a way you understand?		
<p>The study leader should decide if the following question must be asked:</p> <p>Do you understand that we will use your samples and personal information in this and future similar studies in a way that nobody (other than one responsible scientist called the ‘Data Controller’) will know they came from you?</p>		
Do you understand it’s OK to stop taking part at any time?		
Are you happy to take part?		

Please don’t sign your name if you don’t want to take part or if you answered ‘NO’ , to any question!

ANNEX 1.7 - ASSENT FORM FOR CHILDREN

Please write your name and today's date if you want to take part

Your name:	
Today's date:	

Your [**parents/ legal guardians**] must also sign this form:

Parents / guardians full names:	
Parents/ guardians signatures:	
Today's date:	

ANNEX 1.7 - ASSENT FORM FOR CHILDREN

The researcher who explained the study to you must also sign this form:

Researcher's Name:	
Researcher's signature:	
Today's date:	

The following people are happy to hear from you about questions or concerns that you may have:

About the research study: [provide name and contact details of responsible scientist].

About data protection: [provide name, function = Data Protection Officer and contact details].